

Digital Competence and Language Teaching Activities of Junior High School English Teachers in Congressional Teacher II, SDO Batangas Province

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Abstract

This study examined the level of digital competence among public and private junior high school English teachers in the Second Congressional District of Batangas Province across the areas of use of digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learners. It also sought to identify the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching in English instruction particularly in silent reading and reflective writing activities. Moreover, the study identified the challenges Junior High School English teachers experience in utilizing technology in classroom instruction.

The study utilized a descriptive-correlational research design, using a validated survey questionnaire complemented by qualitative narratives. The findings indicated that English teachers in both public and private junior high schools in the Congressional District II of Batangas exhibit moderate digital competence across the four areas examined. The respondents also moderately utilize language teaching activities as to silent reading and reflective writing activities. The findings additionally highlight a strong relationship between teachers' digital competence across all areas and their use of technology-enhanced language teaching activities during silent reading. Notably, there exists a moderate relationship specifically between teachers' digital competence in the use of digital resources and their utilization of technology-enhanced language activities in reflective writing. Furthermore, a strong relationship is observed in the areas of teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learners. However, the respondents also pointed out that various challenges persist limiting the effective integration of digital resources in English instruction. These include access to resources, connectivity issues and limitation in ensuring academic integrity. It is recommended that authorities review evaluate the proposed technology-enhanced language teaching activities and may implement professional development initiatives to sustain and improve teachers' digital competence.

Keywords: *digital competence, language teaching activities, technology-enhanced language teaching, silent reading, reflective writing*

INTRODUCTION

Background and Rationale

The rapid advancement of technology is profoundly influencing human existence, introducing innovations that alter everyday experiences. Particularly in the realm of education, the swift evolution of technological tools has initiated significant transformations in both teaching and learning methodologies. The widespread adoption of digital platforms and resources in educational environments is increasingly evident, fundamentally changing traditional instructional practices and offering new avenues for engagement and interaction among educators and students.

Despite previous initiatives aimed at promoting technological integration within educational settings, the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a pivotal moment for education systems globally, compelling schools to swiftly embrace digital technologies to maintain learning continuity during extended interruptions. This situation initiated a profound transformation in both teaching methodologies and student learning experiences. However, during the lengthy period of school closures, which persisted for over a year, approximately one-third of learners worldwide faced interruptions in their education. This interruption highlighted the urgent necessity to blend technology with human resources to reimagine educational frameworks and create learning systems that are inclusive, adaptable, and resilient (UNESCO, 2024).

The significance of technology in education has not diminished with the subsiding of the pandemic; instead, it has become increasingly vital. Although face-to-face instruction remains the primary mode of learning in schools across the Philippines, various Distance Learning Modalities (DLDMs) such as the Modular Distance Learning (MDL), Online Distance Learning (ODL), TV-Based Instruction (TVI), Radio-Based Instruction (RBI), and blended learning are mandated for implementation by schools and community learning centers, as outlined in DO 22, s.2024, Revised Guidelines on Class and Work Suspension in Schools During Disasters and Emergencies (DepEd Order 12, s.2025).

In line with this, teachers, both in public and private schools, are increasingly expected to integrate technology as a fundamental aspect of their teaching strategies, rather than merely utilizing it as an auxiliary tool. This integration aims to enhance student motivation, engage learners, cultivate communicative proficiency, facilitate effective interactions, and nurture a variety of skills among students.

In this context, the digital competence of teachers has become a crucial element in delivering meaningful and effective instruction. For teachers, digital competence encompasses not only the ability to use devices and software but also the skill to engage with digital tools in a professional manner, curate and design relevant educational resources, integrate technology into teaching and learning, assess student performance effectively, promote digital inclusivity, and

cultivate a supportive learning atmosphere. As the field of education increasingly incorporates technological advancements, it is essential for teachers to cultivate both general digital skills as everyday users and specialized teaching-related digital competencies that will enhance their effectiveness as educators in digital contexts.

In this context, the study sought to examine the level of digital competence among English teachers in the post-pandemic period and to identify the extent of their technology-enhanced language teaching utilization. Ultimately, the study aimed to propose technology-enhanced language teaching activities that will support teachers in effectively integrating technology-enhanced approaches within the English classroom.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of digital competence of Junior High School English teachers and the extent of utilization of language teaching strategies and propose technology-enhanced language teaching activities.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of English teachers' digital competence as assessed by the teachers themselves across the areas of:

- 1.1 use of digital resources;
- 1.2 teaching and learning;
- 1.3 assessment of learning; and
- 1.4 empowering learners?

2. How may the extent of utilization of the language teaching activities be assessed by the respondents with respect to:

- 2.1 silent reading; and
- 2.2 reflective writing?

3. Is there any significant relationship between the assessments of the English teachers' level of digital competence and on the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching in their English classes?

4. What challenges do English teachers encounter in employing technology-enhanced language teaching activities?

5. Based on the results, what technology-enhanced language teaching activities may be proposed?

Hypothesis of the Study

Based on the research questions, the null hypothesis is tested in the study:

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the assessment of teachers' level of digital competence and on the extent of the utilization of language teaching activities in their English classes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational design of quantitative research. The descriptive design was utilized to determine the level of digital competence of English teachers in private and public junior high schools in the Congressional District II, SDO Batangas. The same research design was utilized to assess the extent to which language teaching activities were implemented, particularly focusing on practices related to silent reading and reflective writing. On the other hand, the correlational design was employed to investigate the relationship between teachers' levels of digital competence and their utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching in English classes.

Participants

The respondents of the study were the junior high school English teachers from both private and public schools in the Congressional District II, Schools Division Office Batangas Province for the school year 2025-2026. The respondents consist of 122 English teachers, determined using Raosoft Sample Size Calculator at a 95% confidence level.

Instruments

The primary data collection methods for this study consisted of validated researcher-developed questionnaires and interview questions. These instruments were utilized to evaluate the level of digital competence and the extent of technology-enhanced language teaching integration among private junior high school teachers.

Procedure

To gather the data necessary for this study, the researcher first secured permission to conduct the research by submitting a formal letter of request to the Schools Division Superintendent of the Schools Division Office Batangas. Upon approval, endorsement letters were forwarded to the Public Schools District Supervisors, school heads, and English teachers from both private and public junior high schools within Congressional District II, requesting their assistance and participation in the administration of the survey. Following the approval of

the school administrators, the researcher developed and distributed the questionnaire to the respondents through Google Forms. The online administration of the survey facilitated efficient data collection and ensured accessibility and convenience for the participants.

A Google Form was designed and shared with the intended respondents. The form included a concise description of the purpose of the study, and a statement of consent. The participants were provided ample time to fill the form as per their convenience. Responses were recorded automatically and organized in the Google Sheets for analysis. The anonymity and confidentiality of all the participants were maintained with strictness throughout the data collection process in accordance with Republic Act No. 10173, also referred to as the Data Privacy Act, which protects all types of information, whether it be private, or personal, and only allows it to be used for research aimed at enhancing teaching and learning process.

Data Analysis

To analyze the data collected from the participants, various statistical procedures were employed. Frequency count was employed to determine and clarify the number of responses obtained for each item in the questionnaire. Weighted mean was used to measure the respondents' overall responses, while Pearson's Correlation Coefficient was used to test if there is a significant relationship between English teachers' level of digital competence and the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching in their English classes

RESULTS

1. Teachers' digital competence

1.1 Use of digital resources

The table shows that English teachers generally demonstrate moderate competence in utilizing digital tools and materials to support language instruction, as shown in the composite mean of 3.47, with several indicators reaching a highly competent level. The data further indicates variations in teachers' digital competence, highlighting strengths in evaluating and selecting appropriate digital resources, while also revealing developmental areas in designing and developing technology-enhanced learning activities.

Level of English Teachers' Digital Competence Across the Area of Use of Digital Resources

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. use different internet sites and search strategies to find and select relevant resources	3.50	Highly Competent
2. create visually attractive and effective digital resources	3.34	Moderately

through the use of graphic design tools		Competent
3. modify existing digital resources to adapt them to my needs	3.33	Moderately Competent
4. effectively protect sensitive content, e.g., exams, students' grades, personal data	3.57	Highly Competent
5. align digital learning resources with specific learning objectives	3.51	Highly Competent
6. use appropriate keywords for efficient online searches	3.57	Highly Competent
7. evaluate the credibility and reliability of websites and online sources.	3.59	Highly Competent
8. develop electronic learning activities that promote critical thinking among students	3.24	Moderately Competent
9. select digital sources that are appropriate to students' level and learning needs	3.57	Highly Competent
10. organize and manage digital learning materials for easy access and reuse	3.49	Moderately Competent
Composite Mean	3.47	Moderately Competent

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Competent; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Competent; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Competent; 1.00-1.49=Least Competent

1.2 Teaching and Learning

The table shows the level of English teachers' digital competence across the area of teaching and learning. The results reveal that the respondents demonstrate a moderate competent level in integrating digital technologies into instructional practices (composite mean= 3.37). The distribution of means suggests that educators exhibit greater confidence in planning and decision-making regarding technology integration. In contrast, the participants reported comparatively lower confidence levels in monitoring learner engagement and providing feedback within digital environments.

Level of English Teachers' Digital Competence Across the Area of Teaching and Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. effectively select electronic learning systems to assign and check work remotely	3.35	Moderately Competent
2. allow students to use digital tools to find relevant learning information	3.40	Moderately Competent
3. provide timely, constructive feedback through digital platforms	3.27	Moderately Competent
4. monitor learner engagement in collaborative digital environments	3.26	Moderately Competent
5. select digital tools that support collaboration and meaningful interaction	3.41	Moderately Competent
6. facilitate group learning using digital tools to gather and document evidence of learning	3.35	Moderately Competent
7. use digital technologies to help students plan, document, and monitor learning	3.41	Moderately Competent
8. design digital activities that promote active participation and learner autonomy	3.27	Moderately Competent
9. adapt digital teaching strategies based on student learning data	3.45	Moderately Competent
10. carefully consider how, when, and why to integrate digital technologies in class	3.53	Highly Competent
Composite Mean	3.37	Moderately Competent

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Competent; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Competent; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Competent; 1.00-1.49=Least Competent

1.3 Assessment of Learning

The table shows that English teachers demonstrate a moderately competent level in using digital tools for assessing student learning, with a composite mean of 3.28. This suggested that

teachers are capable of utilizing digital assessment tools for monitoring learning outcomes; however, further development is needed in maximizing advanced assessment features and data analytics to enhance assessment practices.

Level of English Teachers' Digital Competence Across the Area of Assessment of Learning

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. assess students' knowledge and skills with digital tools	3.27	Moderately Competent
2. administer time-bound online assessments that uphold academic integrity	3.22	Moderately Competent
3. integrate digital tools that provide automated feedback on student work	3.18	Moderately Competent
4. employ digital tools that give feedback on correct and incorrect answers after tests	3.27	Moderately Competent
5. utilize digital assessment tools to monitor student progress and outcomes	3.32	Moderately Competent
6. apply digital technologies to give timely, meaningful feedback on learning needs	3.35	Moderately Competent
7. implement accessible digital assessment tools for diverse learning needs	3.33	Moderately Competent
8. analyze digital assessment data to identify learners needing support	3.25	Moderately Competent
9. leverage digital technologies to promote student self-assessment and reflection	3.23	Moderately Competent
10. interpret digital assessment results to improve my teaching strategies	3.37	Moderately Competent
Composite Mean	3.28	Moderately Competent

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Competent; 2.50-3.49= Moderately Competent; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Competent; 1.00-1.49=Least Competent

1.4 Empowering Learners

The table reveals that English teachers possess a moderate competence level (CM= 3.32) in using digital technologies to support learning participation, autonomy, and inclusivity. The distribution of the means indicated that English teachers exhibit a notable competence in facilitating responsible technology utilization and in addressing diverse learning needs. However, their competence appears to be lower when it comes to crafting individualized activities and developing collaborative assignments that extend beyond the traditional classroom setting.

Kalyani (2024) pointed out that the integration of technology in educational settings significantly contributes to student success and the cultivation of vital skills necessary for the 21st century. It encourages collaboration and effective communication among learners, while also enhancing digital literacy, which empowers them to assess and navigate digital information more effectively.

Level of English Teachers' Digital Competence Across the Area of Empowering Learners

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. consider learners' access, digital skills, and technical challenges when creating digital assignments	3.35	Moderately Competent
2. guide students in safe and responsible technology use	3.41	Moderately Competent
3. clarify challenging tasks using digital tools	3.30	Moderately Competent
4. track and communicate students' individual progress using digital tools	3.35	Moderately Competent
5. engage students in learning through digital technologies	3.32	Moderately Competent
6. provide personalized learning activities through digital tools	3.24	Moderately Competent
7. select digital activities that accommodate different learning paces and ability levels	3.40	Moderately Competent
8. design tasks requiring digital communication and collaboration beyond the classroom	3.25	Moderately Competent
9. assign tasks requiring students to create digital content	3.30	Moderately Competent
10. encourage creative problem-solving using digital tools	3.33	Moderately

		Competent
Composite Mean	3.32	Moderately Competent

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Competent; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Competent; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Competent; 1.00-1.49=Least Competent

2. Extent of utilization of language teaching activities

2.1 Silent Reading

The table indicates that English teachers moderately utilize digital tools to enhance silent reading activities, as evidenced by a composite mean of 3.04. The analysis of means demonstrated that there is a greater tendency among teachers to utilize motivational and differential strategies for digital reading. However, it is important to highlight that there is a comparatively lower mean in the adoption of digital reading libraries and the development of structured accessibility features.

Extent of Utilization of Language Teaching Activities with Respect to Silent Reading

I use digital tools to facilitate silent reading in my classroom by...	Mean	Interpretation
1. letting my students explore interactive stories (e.g., multimedia e-books and apps).	3.08	Moderately Utilized
2. providing audio reading models.	3.00	Moderately Utilized
3. tailoring reading experiences to students' individual needs (e.g., adjusted text level, audio support).	3.09	Moderately Utilized
4. offering accessibility supports (e.g., text-to-speech, adjustable fonts, translation tools).	3.02	Moderately Utilized
5. monitoring silent reading progress and comprehension through digital logs or quizzes.	3.06	Moderately Utilized
6. delivering immediate feedback on comprehension or vocabulary via digital quizzes or games.	3.04	Moderately Utilized
7. sparking motivation with gamified reading activities or challenges.	3.16	Moderately Utilized
8. fostering discussion and collaboration about texts through online platforms.	3.06	Moderately Utilized

9. prompting reflection after reading using digital journals, blogs, or boards.	3.07	Moderately Utilized
10. assembling a digital reading library accessible anytime for independent reading.	2.86	Moderately Utilized
Composite Mean	3.04	Moderately Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Utilized; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Utilized; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Utilized; 1.00-1.49=Least Utilized

2.2 Reflective Writing

The table shows that English teachers moderately utilize digital tools to support reflective writing activities, with a composite mean of 3.07, interpreted as often. Furthermore, the results indicate that English teachers prioritize individual reflection supported by digital tools compared to collaborative and process-oriented reflective writing. This suggested that while digital tools are being integrated, there is still room to enhance their use in fostering more collaborative and structured reflective writing experiences.

Extent of Utilization of Language Teaching Activities with Respect to Reflective Writing

I use digital tools to facilitate reflective writing in my classroom by...	Mean	Interpretation
1. providing automated writing and grammar feedback.	3.05	Moderately Utilized
2. letting my students engage in group writing and sharing using collaborative tools.	3.16	Moderately Utilized
3. allowing students to assess their own writing through guided responses.	3.21	Moderately Utilized
4. letting students respond to peer reflection via online comments.	2.94	Moderately Utilized
5. offering digital reflection prompts or guiding questions.	3.08	Moderately Utilized
6. using digital journals or e-portfolios to document and reflect on writing growth.	2.93	Moderately Utilized
7. enabling students to revise reflective writing using version-tracking or draft history.	2.93	Moderately Utilized
8. giving feedback on reflective writing through online	2.98	Moderately Utilized

platforms or LMS.

9. allowing students to include images, audio, or video in their reflective writing.	3.23	Moderately Utilized
10. support students in setting writing goals and reflecting on progress digitally.	3.22	Moderately Utilized
Composite Mean	3.07	Moderately Utilized

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Highly Utilized; 2.50-3.49=Moderately Utilized; 1.50-2.49=Slightly Utilized; 1.00-1.49=Least Utilized

3. Relationship between English Teachers' Level of Digital Competence and the Extent of Utilization of Technology-Enhanced Language Teaching Activities

The table presents the significant relationship between English teachers' level of digital competence and the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching activities in terms of silent reading. The results reveal that all areas of digital competence show strong positive relationship with the utilization technology in silent reading activities, accepting the alternative hypothesis. These findings suggests that the higher levels of teachers' digital competence are associated with more frequent and effective use of digital tools in facilitating silent reading. This further implies that teachers who demonstrate stronger skills in managing digital resources, implementing technology supported instruction, assessing learning digitally, and empowering learners are more likely to integrate technology-enhanced silent reading strategies in their English classes.

Relationship between English Teachers' Level of Digital Competence and the Extent of Utilization of Technology-Enhanced Language Teaching Activities in their English Classes in terms of Silent Reading

Digital Competence	r-value	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision on H ₀	Interpretation
Use of Digital Resources	0.591	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Teaching and Learning	0.645	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Assessment of Learning	0.653	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Empowering Learners	0.621	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Coefficient of correlation (r): +1.0 (Perfect relationship), +.76 to .99 (Very Strong relationship), +.51 to .75 (Strong relationship), +.26-.50 (Moderate Relationship), +.11 to .25

(Weak relationship), $+0.01$ to $.10$ (Very weak relationship), $.00$ (No relationship)

The table illustrates the significant relationship between English teachers' level of digital competence and the extent to which they utilize technology-enhanced language teaching in the context of reflective writing. The statistical analysis showed that all calculated p-values are significant, resulting in the acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. This finding suggested that a greater level of digital competence correlates with a more extensive integration of digital reflective writing activities.

Relationship between English Teachers' Level of Digital Competence and the Extent of Utilization of Technology-Enhanced Language Teaching Activities in their English Classes in terms of Reflective Writing

Digital Competence	r-value	Degree of Relationship	p-value	Decision on H_0	Interpretation
Use of Digital Resources	0.484	Moderate	0.000	Reject	Significant
Teaching and Learning	0.655	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Assessment of Learning	0.634	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant
Empowering Learners	0.593	Strong	0.000	Reject	Significant

Legend: Coefficient of correlation (r): $+1.0$ (Perfect relationship), $+0.76$ to $.99$ (Very Strong relationship), $+0.51$ to $.75$ (Strong relationship), $+0.26$ - $.50$ (Moderate Relationship), $+0.11$ to $.25$ (Weak relationship), $+0.01$ to $.10$ (Very weak relationship), $.00$ (No relationship)

4. Challenges English teachers encounter in employing technology-enhanced language teaching activities

The table presents the challenges encountered by English teachers in employing technology enhanced language teaching activities. The results indicate that teachers generally agreed that several barriers affected their integration of digital tools in English instruction. The distribution of means revealed that infrastructure-related concerns and technical limitations were

the most prominent challenges, while lack of knowledge and confidence in using technology were less evident. This pattern suggested that teachers possessed foundational digital competence, yet external factors such as connectivity, access, and technical support influenced the extent to which technology enhanced activities were implemented in the classroom.

Challenges English Teachers Encounter in Employing Technology-Enhanced Language Teaching Activities

Statements	Mean	Interpretation
1. I lack knowledge of technological tools I can use in teaching English.	2.37	Disagree
2. I need more mentoring or training to fully grasp the use of technology-based instructional tools.	3.03	Agree
3. There is a lack of school-based ICT equipment per class.	2.99	Agree
4. I experience maintenance and technical problems that disrupt the smooth running of the teaching and learning process.	3.11	Agree
5. I have limited time to develop technology-based lessons.	3.00	Agree
6. I lack confidence in using ICT in classroom teaching.	2.31	Disagree
7. Students' unequal access to devices and internet makes it difficult to integrate technology.	3.25	Agree
8. Internet connection in our school is unstable.	3.20	Agree
9. Ensuring academic integrity in online assessments is challenging.	3.15	Agree
10. Rapid changes in technology make it difficult to keep my skills and lessons up to date.	2.89	Agree
Composite Mean	2.93	Agree

Legend: 3.50-4.00=Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49=Agree; 1.50-2.49=Disagree; 1.00-1.49=Strongly Disagree

5. Proposed technology-enhanced language teaching activities

The proposed activities prioritize the use of low-bandwidth and user-friendly digital tools, along with multimodal learning experiences and asynchronous learning approaches, which are crafted to fit the current realities of classroom environments. These strategies are designed to foster student engagement, collaboration, creativity, and differentiated instruction.

- Teachers will participate in workshops led by peers, focusing on accessible applications like Google Docs (offline mode), Quizziz, and Canva. Additionally, they will engage in monthly collaborative sessions to exchange and discuss lesson plans.
- Teachers will create offline reading modules, including PDFs and pre-downloaded audio files, while also advocating for the establishment of community learning hubs that facilitate shared use of devices.
- Students will undertake digital storytelling projects using tools such as PowerPoint and Canva, maintain reflective digital journals, record podcast-style oral practice sessions, and co-author essays in shared Google Docs in offline mode.
- Teachers will utilize digital portfolios, such as Google Drive and OneNote, conduct auto-graded quizzes via platforms like Google Forms and Quizziz, and facilitate exchanges of peer feedback.
- Teachers will systematically map TELT activities to the curriculum map, such as utilizing podcasts to enhance oral fluency and blogs to foster writing skills, while also aligning digital projects with performance tasks.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study indicate that junior high school English teachers exhibit moderate digital competence across the areas of use of digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learning. The respondents also moderately utilize language teaching activities as to silent reading and reflective writing activities. This implies that while teachers effectively employ engaging digital strategies, access to readily available digital reading resources for independent learning may still need further strengthening. Moreover, teachers actively integrate multimedia elements to support reflective writing, the limited use of structured digital tools such as e-portfolios and version tracking suggests a need to strengthen practices that promote continuous writing development and longitudinal reflection.

In terms of silent reading, all four areas of digital competence namely the use of digital resources, teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learners exhibit a strong positive relationship with the utilization of technology enhanced language teaching activities. In contrast, for reflective writing, a moderate relationship is observed between the use of digital resources and technology-enhanced language teaching, while strong relationships are evident between technology utilization and digital competence in the areas of teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learners.

In terms of the challenges English teachers encounter in employing technology-enhanced language teaching activities, teachers generally agree that several barriers affect their integration of digital tools in English instruction. The most significant challenge faced by English teachers is

the unequal access to devices and internet connectivity among students. Interestingly, teachers do not see lack of knowledge or confidence as major issues, which suggests that the problem is more external than personal.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, assessment showed that the level of digital competence of English teachers is moderately competent across the areas of digital resource use, teaching and learning, assessment of learning, and empowering learners. Similarly, the assessment on the use of language teaching activities is moderately utilized in both silent reading and reflective writing. The assessments on the level of digital competence and on the extent of utilization of technology-enhanced language teaching activities indicated significant relationship in all pairs of variables. On the other hand, top three challenges that English teachers encounter in utilizing technology in their classes include students' unequal access to devices and internet, unstable internet connection in schools, and difficulties in ensuring academic integrity in online assessments. Therefore, the proposed language teaching strategies with the integration of technology may help improve how English teachers use technology in teaching.

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